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Effects of soil pH and moisture content on morphology, biomass traits and leaf chlorophyll content of *Voacanga africana* Stapf

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Abstract

Voacanga africana is a small tree with origins from tropical Africa that is significantly represented in the Bamenda Highlands forest of Cameroon. An acidification of soil due to acid rain in the area is being exacerbated by leaching of base cations by the high intensity of the precipitation. There are wide variations in soil moisture content across the landscape. This study investigated the combined effect of soil pH and moisture on growth and chlorophyll content of the species. Five months old seedlings were raised in a greenhouse under two pH levels (neutral; acidic - pH 4.5 - 5) and three moisture regimes (low; intermediate; high) for three months. The treatments were laid out in a split-plot design with pH as the whole plot and the moisture levels as the sub-plots. Data on morphology, biomass, and leaf chlorophyll content were collected at the end of the experiment. Height, root-collar diameter, leaf area, total biomass and that of shoot and root were repressed by the acidic soil pH treatment level. Root: shoot ratio was unaffected by treatments. On the other hand, there was a significant soil pH × moisture effect on leaf chlorophyll content, indicating an increase from the neutral to acidic soil pH with significance only at the intermediate and high moisture regimes. Unlike at the neutral soil pH where the high moisture regime significantly reduced the leaf chlorophyll content, differences among moisture levels were not significant at the acidic pH. Given that the stress imposed by the low soil moisture regime was mild, it is necessary that the low soil moisture content be decreased to severity levels that are characteristic of some portions of the species' range to ascertain if the unresponsiveness of growth to soil pH × moisture interaction is maintained.

Keywords: acid soil, early growth, leaf chlorophyll, montane forest, soil moisture, *Voacanga africana*, Western Highlands of Cameroon

1. Introduction

Voacanga africana is a small evergreen tree that is native to tropical Africa. Commonly known as small-fruited voacanga, the member of the Apocynaceae family grows erect and robust, usually attaining a height of 6 metres with a spreading crown. It is found in East Tropical Africa: Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda; Northeast Tropical Africa: Sudan; South Tropical Africa: Angola, Malawi, Mozambique, Zambia, Zimbabwe; West Tropical Africa: Benin, Burkina, The Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo; West-Central Tropical Africa: Burundi, Cabinda, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo-Brazzaville, Gabon, Gulf of Guinea, DR Congo; with introductions in China (WFO, 2025). The tree is largely used in

customary African medicine in treating a myriad of diseases including malaria, worm infestation, amoebiasis, ulcers, pain, cardiovascular conditions, depression, fatigue, carious teeth, shortness of breath, diarrhea, delayed labour, kidney conditions, asthma, convulsions, sores, abscesses, and fungal infections (Burkil, 1985 – 2004; Bekoe *et al.*, 2024). Aside from the medicinal attributes of the tree, the wood is used locally for building purposes, fuel, making of musical instruments and knife sheaths (Fern, 2024). It is sometimes being grown for ornamental purposes.

The distribution of *Voacanga africana* is highly perceptible within the Western Highlands of Cameroon, which is characterized by a mountainous relief, plains and plateaux. The region is equally home to the largest remaining patches of afro-montane forest in West Africa, growing on an extinct range of volcanoes along mountain ranges. Its relatively fertile soils derived from volcanic rocks and reliable rainfall have attracted a high human population whose activities have been at the detriment of the forest. Major threats to the woodlands include conversion to farmland, fire, grazing, collection of firewood, and unsustainable harvesting of timber and plant parts for construction and medicine. *Voacanga africana* is among the Western Highlands forest flora that are exploited principally for pharmaceutical purposes. Among other uses, its fruit, bark and leaf extracts have been utilized for the treatment of orchitis, ectopic testes and gonorrhoea, respectively, in Cameroonian ethnomedicine (Jiofack *et al.*, 2008; Tan *et al.*, 2000; Hussain *et al.*, 2012; Katjima *et al.*, 2013). The remaining fragments are highly vulnerable to environmental changes from anthropogenic and natural factors.

Meanwhile, soil pH is a dominant factor influencing plant growth and development through its control of nutrient availability for uptake by roots (Tang *et al.*, 2001). Some mineral elements such as iron, zinc, manganese and copper are more available at low pH, while others such as molybdenum, calcium and magnesium become more available for uptake as the pH increases (Marschner, 2005). Too low soil pH levels can however, result in micronutrient toxicities. Such is the case with manganese, aluminum and iron which become available at toxic levels when pH drops to below 4.0 (Soils West, 2024). In contrast, molybdenum and zinc deficiencies commonly occur under acidic and alkaline conditions respectively (VRO, 2020). Apart from the effects on nutrient availability, root growth is also constrained by soil acidity (Haling *et al.*, 2011), placing additional limitations on plant access to belowground resources. The Bamenda Highlands that constitute part of the Western Highlands of Cameroon is within the ecological range of *Voacanga africana*. Acidic rainfall has been reported in this region (Ntabe *et al.*, 2005; Wirmvem *et al.*, 2014), a characteristic that has impacted the pH of the soil. The acidic soil condition is slowly but continuously being exacerbated by excessive leaching of base cations (Ca, Mg, K, Na) by the typically heavy rainfall of the region (Yerima *et al.*, 2020). The decrease in soil pH may pose an additional constraint to the growth and development of the ecosystem's flora.

Equally, soil moisture which is another abiotic factor limiting the growth and development of forest plants, has suffered from wide variations, imposed by an array of topographic features across the landscape. It is important to note that ecosystem factors do not necessarily affect plants in isolation. In contrast, they often interact with each other to influence physiological, growth, developmental and other aspects of plants in ways that do not obviously reflect the direct sum of individual effects. Moreover, the response may be species specific. Understanding differential seedling responses to ecosystem conditions is therefore crucial for envisioning forest trajectories. This study was aimed at investigating the combined effects of soil pH and moisture availability on growth and leaf chlorophyll content of *Voacanga africana*. The seedling stage was considered for this trial as it constitutes a significant bottleneck for forest regeneration.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area

The greenhouse experiment was conducted at the Department of Forestry and Wildlife Technology of The University of Bamenda (lat. 6°0'45" N; long. 10°15'27" E; alt. 1444 m). The institution is located in Bambili, one of the four main villages, which together with Bambui, Kedjo-ketinguh and Kedjom-keku make up the Tubah municipality of the North West Region of Cameroon. Bambili falls within the tropical monsoon climatic type and is characterised by a rainy and dry season (Ntabe *et al.*, 2022). The former starts from March to September, while the later spans from September to March. However, the start and duration of the seasons haven't been constant in recent years, due to changing global climatic conditions. On an annual average, the area experiences a rainfall index of about 2095 mm, and a mean temperature of 22.51 °C. The greatest rainfall occurs in July, August, and September (over 350 mm/month), while lowest rainfall is experienced in the month of January (6 mm). February and August are the warmest and coldest months, with average high - low temperatures of 29.8 - 16.1 and 21.6 - 15.6 °C respectively (Weather Atlas, 2024). During the course of the experiment, we followed the ambient weather conditions to manually manage the climate of the greenhouse as the structure was not equipped with an automated regulation system.

2.2. Experimental design

Treatments were comprised of two pH (7; 4.5 - 5) and three moisture (low; intermediate; high) regimes. The treatments were laid out in a split-plot design with two replications. Soil pH was the main plot, and moisture was the sub-plot. The acid pH treatment level was attained by adding drops of concentrated sulphuric acid to normal tap (pH 7). A pH meter stuck in the substrate was used to ensure that the target pH range was not compromised at irrigation. On the other hand, the soil moisture content was varied by modifying irrigation frequency. The low moisture treatment level entailed watering seedlings once a week, while the intermediate and high moisture regimes corresponded to a 3- and 5-times weekly irrigation rate, respectively.

Plant material was comprised of 5 months old *Voacanga africana* seedlings, raised in the nursery of the Reforestation Task Force, a local community-based organisation, operating in neighbouring Bamenda III municipality (lat. 6°15'0" - 6°25'0" N; long. 10°02'0" - 10°15'0" E). They were grown in polythene bags filled with soil. In each treatment and replication were ten seedlings of uniform size, and without any visual defect. Any weed that emerged from the substrate was immediately hand-picked, and the treatments lasted for three months (from 5 March to 5 June 2024).

2.3. Data collection

At the end of the trial, measurements of morphological, biomass, and leaf chlorophyll content were conducted on three randomly selected plants per treatment. Plant height was determined with a ruler as the distance from the soil surface to the tip of the shoot after which root-collar was measured with a Vernier caliper. The number of leaves produced during the course of the treatments was recorded, and the most fully expanded was tagged for measurement of chlorophyll and area. The chlorophyll content was taken to be the average of three measurements, carried out at the upper third, middle and lower third of the upper surface of the leaf with a SPAD-502 Chlorophyll Meter (Konica-Minolta Co. Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). Following the chlorophyll measurement, the leaf was harvested, spread on a graph paper and its margin traced. The leaf area was noted from the number of 1 cm² and 0.04 cm² cells *in-situ* the traced region. Soil was carefully washed off the roots and the seedling decapitated at the root-shoot junction. Each of the fragments was dried in an oven to constant weight and weighed. The root: shoot ratio was calculated from the dry weight of the fractions.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Data were examined graphically for normality and homoscedasticity. When they were found to fulfil the ANOVA assumptions, the effects of soil pH, moisture, and their interaction on morphology, biomass, and leaf chlorophyll content were tested with split-plot ANOVA. Means separation for the interactive effect of treatments on leaf chlorophyll content was conducted with Scheffe's test. The analyses were conducted in Data Desk 6.01 at $p = 0.1$.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Growth

With the exception of number of new leaves and root: shoot ratio, there was a significant effect of soil pH on all morphological and biomass parameters. However, the effect on leaf area, shoot and total biomass were only marginally significant. In contrast, no morphological or biomass trait was markedly influenced by either soil moisture content alone, or its various combinations with the pH (Table 1).

Table 1: *p*-values from ANOVA for the effects of soil pH, moisture, and their interaction on morphology, biomass, and leaf chlorophyll content

Source	Soil pH	Soil moisture	Soil pH × moisture
Height	0.0442	0.8442	0.5296
Root-collar diameter	0.0493	0.4419	0.8615
Number of leaves	0.3117	0.1963	0.296
Leaf area	0.1231	0.9242	0.9171
Shoot mass	0.1321	0.8934	0.5579
Root mass	0.0894	0.6595	0.8967
Total mass	0.1068	0.9252	0.7335
Root : Shoot mass	0.4348	0.6417	0.7612
Leaf chlorophyll content	0.656	0.1449	0.1005

The trend of response was common for all of the variables. Height, root-collar diameter, leaf area, total biomass and that of shoot and root were significantly reduced by the pH 4.5 – 5 treatment level (Figure 1, 2). The findings of this study corroborate the report of Robles-Aguilar *et al.* (2019) that total biomass of narrow-leaf lupine (*Lupinus angustifolius*) is 65% less in pH 4.5 than pH-neutral soil. Furthermore, height, fresh weight, total area of leaf and root of sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris*) experienced significant declines under acidic soil conditions (Geng *et al.*, 2021). The growth reductions may be attributed to limited water and nutrient absorption imposed by an impairment of root growth in the acidic condition. In the present study, the repression of root biomass by the acidic soil pH was accompanied by visible diminutions in root elongation and branching. Aluminum toxicity has been blamed for the restrained root growth in acid soil (Haling *et al.*, 2011). Al³⁺ reduces both root cell division and root elongation, resulting in short, stubby roots (Berkelaar, 2001). Unlike at soil pH ≥ 5.5 when aluminum is strongly bound to insoluble inorganic matter and unavailable for uptake by plant roots, an increasingly greater proportion is found either in soil solution or loosely associated with inorganic matter when pH declines to below 5.5 (Berkelaar, 2001; Rahman *et al.*, 2024). As observed in paper birch (*Betula papyrifera*), on the other hand, a low pH related decline in plant growth could be related to a decrease in root water flow rate and hydraulic conductivity induced by a modification of water channel function (Kamaluddin and Zwiazek, 2004).

Figure 1: Effect of soil pH and moisture content on morphology.

Values are mean \pm SE. The letters above the means indicate the effect of pH while their absence indicates non-significant effect of treatments. Means underneath different letters differ significantly.

The soil pH modifications of plant growth may also result from the influence of this factor on the functioning and abundance of beneficial soil fauna. Low pH decreases the activities of bacteria for the decomposition of organic matter so that nutrients remain locked therein. For instance, nitrogen becomes available to plants when the pH of the soil is increased to above 5.5 and phosphorus is obtainable at a soil pH of between 6.0 and 7.0 (Dobbins, 2021). The slow pace of decomposition in acidic soil may also be explained by a reduction in growth / number of detritivores which, in addition, also compromises soil structure (Ahmed and Al-Mutairi, 2022). While decomposing microbes are abundant in neutral and slightly acidic soils, detritivores are richly represented in neutral and slightly alkaline media.

According to the theory of functional balance, plants respond to limited water availability with a relative increase in the flow of assimilates to the root (Brouwer, 1963; Thornley, 1972). Consequently, root: shoot ratio of the seedlings was expected to be augmented by the low moisture regime. A high root: shoot ratio is suggestive of a relatively high water absorptive and low transpiration area for sustaining growth under unfavourable soil moisture conditions. In disagreement with the model, however, the parameter was unresponsive to moisture availability in the present investigation (Table 1, Figure 2). It

appears that the soil moisture content due to the low moisture treatment level was mild and insufficient to trigger a greater flow of assimilates to the roots of the 5-month old seedlings of *Voacanga africana*. However, seedlings may experience greater degrees of water stress under field conditions leading to moisture-related differences in root: shoot ratio at neutral but not necessarily acidic soil pH where root growth is generally suppressed, with the outcome that soil pH \times moisture interaction is significant.

Figure 2: Effect of soil pH and moisture content on biomass.

Values are mean \pm SE. The letters above the means indicate the effect of pH while their absence indicates non-significant effect of treatments. Means underneath different letters differ significantly.

3.2. Leaf Chlorophyll content

Chlorophyll is the central pigment of photosynthesis that captures and transfers energy to the reaction centre. Measurement of leaf chlorophyll content can potentially inform on the influence of stress on metabolic processes of a plant (Novianti *et al.*, 2020). In this study, there was a marginally significant effect of soil moisture, but not pH, on leaf chlorophyll content. Additionally, the effect of soil pH \times moisture was also marginally significant for the trait (Table 1). Values generally increased from the 7 to 4.5 – 5 pH treatment level where moisture levels did not differ for one another for the parameter. However, the augmentations due to the acidic pH treatment level were only

significant at the intermediate and high moisture regimes. At pH 7, on the other hand, leaf chlorophyll content was significantly lower at the high than the other moisture levels that showed a common response for the trait (Figure 3). Consistent with our finding, chlorophyll content of *Epipremnum aureum* was found to be reduced by high moisture availability in a previous study. Furthermore, there was a tendency for an increase in values of the trait from the neutral to an acidic pH soil (Hu and Lee, 2022), as also detected in this study

Figure 3: Effect of soil pH and moisture content on leaf chlorophyll content. Values are mean \pm SE. The letters above the means indicate the effect of soil pH \times moisture. Means underneath different letters differ significantly.

4. Conclusion

Generally, the acidic soil pH (4.5 – 5) had an adverse effect on the early growth of *Voacanga africana*. To some extent, in contrast, it was beneficial to leaf chlorophyll content. Given that the stress level imposed by the low soil moisture level was mild, it is necessary that much lower soil moisture contents characteristic of some portions of the species' range be tested to ascertain if the unresponsiveness of growth to soil pH \times moisture interaction is maintained.

5. References

- Ahmed, N. and Al-Mutairi, K.A. (2022). Earthworms effect on microbial population and soil fertility as well as their interaction with agriculture practices. *Sustainability* 14: 7803.
- Bekoe, E.O., Opare, J.A.A., Lartey, M. and Amoateng, P. (2024). Ethnomedicinal uses, biological activities, and toxicity of *Voacanga africana* Stapf Ex Scott-Elliot. *Advances in Traditional Medicine* 24: 431-448.

- Berkelaar, E. 2001. The Effect of Aluminum in Acidic Soils on Plant Growth. ECHO Development Notes no. 71.
- Brouwer, R. (1963). Some aspects of the equilibrium between overground and underground plant parts. Jaarboek IBS, Wageningen.
- Burkil, H.M. (1985 - 2004). The useful plants of west tropical Africa. Royal Botanic Garden, Kews.
- Dobbins, I. (2021). The effect of soil pH on plants. Southland Organics. https://www.southlandorganics.com/blogs/news/the-effect-of-soil-ph-on-plants?srsltid=AfmBOoqTfz4e3qOV0upx_Clir-5L-2JA2ub2JgKEMSVir2siimprVp0i. (Accessed 27.01.2025).
- Fern, K. (2024). Useful tropical plants. *Voacanga africana*. Tropical Plants Database. <https://tropical.theferns.info/viewtropical.php?id=Voacanga+africana>. (Accessed 14.01.2025).
- Geng, G., Wang, G., Stevanato, P., Lv, C., Wang, Q., Yu, L. and Wang, Y. (2021) Physiological and proteomic analysis of different molecular mechanisms of sugar beet response to acidic and alkaline pH environment. *Frontiers in Plant Sciences* 12: 682799.
- Haling, R.E., Simpson, R.J., Culvenor, R.A., Lambers, H. and Richardson, A.E. (2011). Effect of soil acidity, soil strength and macropores on root growth and morphology of perennial grass species differing in acid-soil resistance. *Plant, Cell and Environment* 34, 444-456.
- Huh, M.K. and Lee, B. (2022). The change of chlorophyll content and chlorophyll efficiency in *Epipremnum aureum* by water and pH. *European Journal of Botany* 1: 1-5.
- Hussain, H., Hussain, J., Al-Harrasi, A. and Green, I.R. (2012). Chemistry and biology of the genus *Voacanga*. *Pharmaceutical Biology* 50: 1183-1193.
- Jiofack, T., Fokunang, C., Kemeuze, V., Fongnzossie, E., Tsabang, N., Nkuinkeu, R., Mapongmetsem, P.M. and Nkongmeneck, B.A. (2008). Ethnobotany and phytopharmacopoea of the South-West ethnoecological region of Cameroon. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research* 2: 197-206.
- Kitajima, M., Iwai, M., Kogure, N., Kikura-Hanajiri, R., Goda, Y. and Takayama, H. (2013) Aspidosperma-aspidosperma-type bisindole alkaloids from *Voacanga africana*. *Tetrahedron* 69: 796-801.
- Kamaluddin, M. and Zwiazek, J.J. (2004). Effects of root medium pH on water transport in paper birch (*Betula papyrifera*) seedlings in relation to root temperature and abscisic acid treatments. *Tree Physiology* 24: 1173-1180.
- Marschner, H. (2005). Mineral Nutrition of Plants. Academic Press Inc.
- Novianti, V., Rachmawati, D., Indradewa, D. and Maryani (2020). The effect of low pH on physiological characters in vegetative phase of Kalimantan local swamp rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *AIP Conference Proceedings* 2260: 030019.

- Ntabe E.N, Ngueguim J.T, Gautam S.H, Larinde S.G and Nkwatoh A.F (2022). Growth modelling of *Eucalyptus grandis* W.Hill ex Maiden TOOLUR in the north-western highlands of Cameroon. *World News of Natural Sciences* 44: 294-307.
- Ntabe E.N.; Ajonina G. N.; Mbong G.A.; and Tieguhong J.C. (2005). Effects of natural manure on the early growth characteristics of *Artemisia annua* L in Dschang-Cameroon. *Journal of Science, Technology and Environment* 5: 1-5.
- Rahman, S.U., Han, J.C., Ahmad, M., Ashraf, M.N., Khaliq, M.A., Yousaf, M., Wang, Y., Yasin, G., Nawaz, M.F., Khan, K.A. and Du, Z. (2024). Aluminum phytotoxicity in acidic environments: A comprehensive review of plant tolerance and adaptation strategies. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 269: 115791.
- Robles-Aguilar, A. A., Pang, J., Postma, J. A., Schrey, S. D. Lambers, H. and Jablonowski, N. D. (2019). The effect of pH on morphological and physiological root traits of *Lupinus angustifolius* treated with struvite as a recycled phosphorus source. *Plant and Soil* 434: 65-78.
- Soils West (2024). Soil quality knowledge base. <https://www.soilqualityknowledgebase.org.au> (Accessed 23.12.2024).
- Tan, P.V., Penlap, V.B., Nyasse, B. and Nguemo, J.D.B. (2000). Anti-ulcerations of the bark methanol extract of *Voacanga africana* in different experimental ulcer models in rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 73: 423-428.
- Tang, C., Diatloff, E., Rengel, Z. and McGann, B. (2001). Growth response to subsurface soil acidity of wheat genotypes differing in aluminium tolerance. *Plant and Soil* 236: 1-10.
- Thornley, J.H.M. 1972. A balanced quantitative model for root: shoot ratios in vegetative plants. *Annals of Botany* 36: 431-441.
- VRO (2020). Toxicities and deficiencies. Victorian Resources Online, State of Victoria (Agriculture Victoria) 1996 - 2024.
- Weather Atlas (2024). Climate and monthly weather forecast Bambili, Cameroon. <https://www.weather-atlas.com/en/cameroon/bambili-climate> (Accessed 29.07.2024).
- WFO (2025). *Voacanga africana* Stapf ex Scott Elliot. Published on the Internet; <http://www.worldfloraonline.org/taxon/wfo-0000333604>. (Accessed 08.01.2025).
- Wirmvem, M.J., Ohba, T., Fantong, W.Y., Ayonghe, S.N., Hogarh, J, N, Suila, J, Y, Asaah, A.N., Ooki, S., Tanyileke, G. and Hell, J.V. (2014). Origin of major ions in monthly rainfall events at the Bamenda Highlands, North West Cameroon. *Journal of Environmental Sciences* 26(4): 801-809.
- Yerima, B.P.K., Enang, R.K., Kome, G.K. and Van Ranst E. (2020). Exchangeable aluminium and acidity in Acrisols and Ferralsols of the north-west highlands of Cameroon. *Geoderma Regional* 23: e00343.